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ABSTRACT

The ARIES WP15 program deals with the optimization of superconducting films for the use in accelerating structures. In the present approach, all production steps necessary to arrive at a successful coating are revisited, from substrate preparation to sample handling to the actual film deposition. These steps are performed on wafer samples, and in an intermediate step, prior to doing an actual coating on cavities, on QPR-samples (Quadrupole Resonator-samples) that allow for a characterisation under real accelerator-like conditions. In continuation of the previously reported results, sample manufacturing and DC-characterisation has progressed towards two additional systems: NbN and SIS. The procedures leading to an optimized sample are described in detail.

Characterisation of the samples with standard materials characterisation methods as well as DC-magnetometry has been performed and is reported. RF-characterisation was performed on baseline Nb QPR-samples, comparing the coating results between the facilities at STFC and USI and the impact of the substrate preparation technique on the quality of the obtained film.

ARIES Consortium, 2020

For more information on ARIES, its partners and contributors please see <http://aries.web.cern.ch>

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Executive summary

Following the WP15 program, sample manufacturing and DC-characterisation has progressed towards two new systems: NbN with AlN as SIS multilayer and NbTiN samples. The procedures that were optimized to create samples with these coatings and their evaluation with state of the art inspection techniques are described in detail. Furthermore, superconductivity evaluation was performed on these samples with DC magnetometry.

In the subsequent step, pursuing the WP15 goals, QPR-samples were prepared. The procedures that were optimized for the small samples had to be adapted which is described in detail. This entails substrate preparation and film deposition. RF-characterisation was performed on baseline Nb QPR-samples, comparing the Nb coating results between the facilities at STFC and USI and the impact of the substrate preparation technique optimized at INFN Legnaro. The ultimate goal of characterising the RF properties of novel material thin films had to be delayed towards the end of the project.

1. Introduction

The scope and the roadmap of WP15 programme has been set before the ARIES project starting date. All activities of WP15 are connected and integrated in one international project. The D15.1 Delivery Report summarised the WP15 progress with Evaluation of copper substrate cleaning and polishing process. Two procedure for surface preparation of Cu for Nb coating was chosen for the following WP15 activities base on various types of characterisation of copper surface and Nb film deposited on it [1]. The following activities were focused on developing the thin films (TF) based on superconducting (SC) materials different from pure Nb. The choice of materials was discussed in details in the D15.1 and D15.2 Deliverable Reports [2, 3] and based on literature survey [4-8]. The developing and evaluation of Systems 1 (Nb₃Sn) and System 2 (NbN) has been reported describing the details of deposition, surface analysis, structural analysis, and DC superconductivity evaluation.

This report is related to the next stage of SC TF development: System 3 (NbTiN) and SIS (superconductor-insulator-superconductor) multilayer coatings. A considerable fraction of the work summarized here has been presented at various journals or conferences, see [9-15]. As a reminder, the requirements for an alternative SC thin film are listed below, once more:

1. It must be possible to fabricate it in a way that it conforms to a complex geometry over large area.
2. It must have decent thermal conductivity (and be able to be deposited on a substrate with decent thermal conductivity) for cooling to avoid thermal runaway.
3. It must have minimal surface roughness to avoid field enhancement.
4. It must be producible in a clean manner (for example, it cannot release potentially field emitting dust, and there must be a method to clean surface contaminants without affecting quality).

The properties of the investigated alternative materials are shown in Table 1, along with those of niobium.

Table 1: Some superconducting parameters for materials for SRF applications investigated within WP15.

Material	T_c (K)	ρ_n ($\mu\Omega\text{cm}$)	$H_c(0)$ (T)	$H_{c1}(0)$ (T)	$H_{c2}(0)$ (T)	λ (nm)	Δ (meV)	ξ (nm)
Nb	9.23	2	0.2	0.18	0.28	40	1.5	35
NbN	17.3	70	0.23	0.02	15	200-350	2.6	3-5
NbTiN	17.8	35	-	0.03	15	150-200	2.8	5
Nb ₃ Sn	18	8-30	0.54	0.05	28	80-100	3.1	4

Another significant part of the WP15 activities is focused on evaluation of SC TF at the conditions similar to ones in accelerator radio-frequency (RF) resonators. The Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) developed in earlier H2020 projects is employed for this activity [16]. This Report describes new QPR samples, developing cleaning and polishing procedure, Nb TF deposition and, finally, testing at the RF conditions at HZB and CERN.

2. Developing of SC thin film coating on samples

The consortium continues developing coatings with thin film of superconducting materials different from Nb, such as Nb₃Sn, NbN, NbTiN as well as SIS multilayer structures. The deposition performed on the samples prepared in Year 1: flat OHFC samples with dimensions 53 mm × 53 mm × 2 mm. The samples are polished with either SUBU or EP, two polishing procedures defined as most promising in Year 1 [2].

2.1 DEPOSITION AT STFC

2.1.1 System 3: NbTiN thin films

2.1.1.1 Background

Niobium titanium nitride has been suggested as an alternative to niobium nitride as it has much smaller normal state resistivity, reported as low as 37 $\mu\Omega\text{cm}$ and, therefore, would be expected to display small R_{BCS} at 4.2 K. The T_c of niobium titanium nitride is 17.3 K, ξ is 5 nm and λ_0 is 150 - 200 nm [19].

2.1.1.2 Preparation of NbTiN films

Niobium titanium nitride films were deposited by dual magnetron sputtering. One magnetron, fitted with a 99.95 % niobium target, was powered by the HiPIMS power supply. A second magnetron,

fitted with a 99.99 % titanium target, was powered by the pulsed DC power supply. Both targets were maintained at 150 mm from the substrate surface. The HiPIMS power supply was set to pulse with a repetition rate of 1000 Hz with 50 μ s pulse length whilst the pulsed DC supply was set to pulse at 350 kHz with a 50% duty cycle. Films were deposited with a constant current of 590 mA supplied to the niobium cathode and 960 mA supplied to the titanium cathode. The process gas was a mixture of krypton and nitrogen at 7×10^{-3} mbar and the silicon (100) substrate was heated to 600 °C. Similarly, the nitrogen partial pressure was varied between 11 and 21% across the set of deposited samples.

The resistance of deposited samples was measured using the four-point probe with a current of 1 mA. Figure 1 displays the resistance versus temperature data for the niobium titanium nitride films. The resistance versus temperature curves suggest that the normal state DC resistance of the niobium titanium nitride is inversely proportional to the nitrogen content for all partial pressures that were tested. The resistance measured across the four-point probe reduced with

Figure 1: Resistance versus temperature curves for niobium titanium nitride thin films deposited with a range of nitrogen partial pressures. a) displays the curve between 0 and 100 K whilst b) displays the superconducting transition.

increasing nitrogen partial pressure from a maximum of 19.5 mΩ at 11% nitrogen down to 0.4 mΩ at 21% nitrogen.

Samples showed no superconductivity when deposited with a nitrogen partial pressure of 11%. Samples were superconducting at a partial pressure between 14 and 21 % nitrogen, the maximum $T_c = 16.67 \pm 0.01$ K occurred at 20% (see Figure 2. The shape of the T_c versus nitrogen partial pressure curve displays a plateau where T_c did not vary by more than 0.3 K between nitrogen partial pressures of 17 and 21%. Figure 3 displays a cross sectional SEM image of the niobium titanium nitride sample with the largest T_c , deposited with a 20% nitrogen partial pressure. The SEM image showed the film thickness to be 350 ± 30 nm. Measurement of the film thickness allowed the resistivity of the sample to be calculated at $45 \pm 7 \mu\Omega \times \text{cm}$.

Only two niobium titanium nitride thin films were analysed using XRD; the measurements are shown in Figure 4. The samples were deposited with constant niobium cathode current of 590 mA, constant titanium cathode current of 960 mA and either 14 or 20% nitrogen partial pressure. Each XRD measurement shows peaks indicating that the niobium titanium nitride has formed with a preferred fcc (111) orientation, with a smaller peak denoting the (200) orientation. The XRD spectra are similar for each of the tested samples. The length of a_0 from the (111) peak results in 4.39 ± 0.01 and 4.41 ± 0.01 Å for the films deposited in nitrogen partial pressure of 14 or 20% respectively.

Figure 2: The T_c of niobium titanium nitride thin films with varying nitrogen partial pressure during deposition.

The SEM image showed the film thickness to be 350 ± 30 nm. Measurement of the film thickness allowed the resistivity of the sample to be calculated at $45 \pm 7 \mu\Omega \times \text{cm}$.

Figure 3: SEM image of a niobium titanium nitride thin film deposited with a niobium cathode current of 590 mA, a titanium cathode current of 960 mA and a nitrogen partial pressure of 20%. T_c of the sample was 16.67 ± 0.01 K.

RBS was used to analyse two niobium titanium nitride thin films to provide the elemental composition of the samples. The samples were deposited with either 18 or 20% nitrogen partial pressure. The RBS measurement of the sample deposited in a partial pressure of 20% nitrogen is shown in Figure 5, including a summary table of both measurements. The summary table shows that the titanium content remained constant but the niobium was replaced by nitrogen as its partial pressure was increased during deposition.

The normal state resistance of the samples deposited for this study decreased up to the largest tested nitrogen partial pressure suggesting that the nitrogen content did not reach optimal concentrations; this was confirmed by the RBS data. The stoichiometry for perfect niobium titanium nitride crystal would constitute 25 at.% of niobium, 25 at.% of titanium and 50 at.% of

Figure 4: XRD data for niobium titanium nitride thin films deposited with a niobium cathode current of 590 mA, titanium cathode current of 960 mA and nitrogen partial pressure of either 14 or 20%.

nitrogen. The closest to perfect composition from the measured films was 37.7% niobium, 16.2% titanium and 46.1% nitrogen for the sample with the largest $T_c = 16.67 \pm 0.01$ K.

The film with the largest $T_c = 16.67$ K had a thickness measured at 350 nm and therefore the resistivity of the sample could be calculated. The resistivity of the sample was $45 \pm 7 \mu\Omega \times \text{cm}$.

The next step is to deposit NbTiN from an alloy target where optimum stoichiometry NbTiN can be achieved.

Figure 5: Rutherford backscattering spectroscopy measurement of a niobium titanium nitride thin film deposited with a niobium cathode current of 590 mA, a titanium cathode current of 960 mA and a nitrogen partial pressure of 20%. T_c of the sample was 16.67 ± 0.01

2.1.2 Deposition with TiNb alloy target:

NbTi and NbTiN were deposited from a NbTi alloy target on various diamond turned copper and various witness substrate at RT and 650 °C with deposition parameters showed in Table 2.

Table 2: List of samples and deposition parameters and layer structure.

Date Sample ID	Sub (witness)	Power supply	DC Bias (V)	Deposition temperature (°C)	Time (min), Thickness (nm), Power (W), Current (A), Voltage (V)				
					Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	(4)	(5)
30/07/19	Diamond turned Cu Ta Si VC	DC	0	RT	NbTiN 93 50:50 N - 300 0.61 490	NbTiN 30 100% N - 300 0.58 518			
02/08/19	Diamond turned Cu Ta Si VC	DC	0	650	NbTiN 180 - 300 0.60 502				
06/08/19	Diamond turned Cu Ta Si VC	DC	0	650	NbTi 180 - 300 0.70 431				
14/08/19	Diamond turned Cu Ta Si VC	DC	0	HEATED FOR 3 DAYS 650°C	Nb 52 - 400 0.96 416	NbTi 68 - 300 0.74 406	NbTi 50:50 N/Kr 60 300 0.62 486		

Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) option of the commercial PPMS system (model 6000) from Quantum Design Inc. The magnetic moment m was measured in dependence on monotonically increasing (or decreasing) applied field H , recording the so-called magnetization curves $m(H)$. The magnetization curves were measured on samples cooled down below T_c in zero applied magnetic field (zero-field-cooled conditions, ZFC). The external magnetic field was applied parallel to the flat face of the samples. The main characteristic determined from the magnetization curves is the so-called first flux entry field H_{en} . The critical temperature measurement showed that only film deposited at elevated temperature had superconducting properties with T_c of 14.3 K for NbTiN and 9.6 K for NbTi. In both cases the first flux entry field H_{en} was well below the expected value (see Figure 31 in section 2.4) however the higher critical field of H_{c2} was determined to be above 16 T.

2.1.3 Multilayer films

2.1.3.1 Nb₃Sn Multilayer as SIS on copper and sapphire

First SIS systems were produced and studied. The SIS multilayer has deposited at STFC using the condition above which has been discussed in the Delivery report D15.2 and shown in Table 3.

Table 3: List of samples and deposition parameters and layer structure.

Date Sample ID	Substrate (witness)	Power supply	DC Bias (V)	Dep. temp (°C)	Time (min), Thickness (nm), Power (W), Current (A), Voltage (V)				
					Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	Layer 4	Layer 5
18/02/19 A15-19	Cu (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb	AlN	Nb ₃ Sn	AlN	Nb ₃ Sn
					208	7	5	7	5
					-	-	-	-	-
					400	202	200	202	200
					1.17	1.02	0.53	0.98	0.54
358	196	378	203	368					
					(350 kHz, 1.1 μs)		(350 kHz, 1.1 μs)		
21/02/19 A15-20	Sapphire (Ta, Sapphire)	DC	0	650	Nb	AlN	Nb ₃ Sn	AlN	Nb ₃ Sn
					247	7	5	7	5
					-	-	-	-	-
					400	202	200	202	200
					1.11	0.98	0.54	1.03	0.56
362	204	372	195	357					
					(350 kHz, 1.1 μs)		(350 kHz, 1.1 μs)		

The SEM micrograph is shown in Figure 6. As it can be seen the first layer of insulating layer of AlN between the Nb and Nb₃Sn has not been uniformly deposited. However, the second insulating layer of AlN between the two Nb₃Sn layers is uniform and follows the topography of the layer below. The observed anomaly was first attributed to mixing during the deposition. However, later it was found that the anomaly is due to initial sample polishing prior to ion beam milling. This was rectified in preparing X-section SEM sample for the next system.

2.1.3.2 NbTiN Multilayer as SIS on copper

NbTiN multilayer as SIS structure were deposited from a NbTi alloy target on various diamond turned copper and various witness substrate at RT and 650°C with deposition parameters showed in Table 4.

The substrate was heated to 650°C for 20 hours prior to deposition to remove the top oxide layer for better adhesion and annealing any mechanical stress produced during diamond turning. Additional witness samples of Ta, Sapphire and vitreous carbon are also deposited to facilitate various

complementary surface and compositional analysis as well as studying the effect of substrate on the synthesised Nb thin film.

The SEM micrograph is shown in Figure 7. As it can be seen the SIS structure are well preserved during the ion milling contraire to what was seen in the case of Nb₃Sn SIS sample (distortion of the AlN due to mechanical polishing prior to ion beam milling). The layers are well separated with no observable inter-mixing of individual layers both in SEM contrast micrographs and EDS compositional mapping. It can be seen that the 50 to 60 nm NbTiN layers are separated by the 12 to 15 nm AlN layer.

Rutherford back scattering (RBS) analysis was performed on all the samples to determine the stoichiometry of each layer. Figure 8 depicts the RBS spectra for sample (19/08/19) deposited on sapphire witness substrate. The layers thickness and composition are summarised in Table 5.

Figure 6: Sample A15-19, (a) High resolution SEM of ion milled X-section of SIS multilayer structure deposited on Ta. (b) EDX chemical mapping of the X-section.

Table 4: List of samples and deposition parameters and layer structure.

Date Sample ID	Sub (witness)	Power supply	DC Bias (V)	Dep temp (°C)	Time (min), Thickness (nm), Power (W), Current (A), Voltage (V)				
					Layer 1	Layer 2	Layer 3	Layer 4	L5
16/08/19	Diamond turned Cu, Ta, Si, VC	DC (AlN→ Pulsed DC)	0	650	Nb	AlN ^{1 2}	NbTiN ^{1 2}	Bi layer AlN/NbTiN	
					120	7	5		
					-	10	28		
					400	200	300		
					0.99	1.01	0.62		
404	199	485	3						
19/08/19	Diamond turned Cu, Ta, Si, VC	DC (AlN→ Pulsed DC)	0	650	Nb	AlN ^{1 2}	NbTiN ^{1 2}	Bi layer AlN/NbTiN	
					300	7	5		
					-	10	28		
					400	200	300		
					0.99	1.01	0.63		
406	199	477	3						
21/08/19	Diamond turned Cu Ta Si VC	DC (AlN→ Pulsed DC)	0	650	Nb	AlN ^{1 2}	NbTiN ^{1 2}	Bi layer AlN/NbTiN	
					120	7	10		
					-	10	60		
					400	200	300		
					0.99	1.01	0.65		
406	199	461	3						
30/08/19	Diamond turned Cu, Ta, Si, VC, Sapphire	DC (AlN→ Pulsed DC)	0	650	Nb	AlN ^{1 2}	NbTiN ^{1 2}	Bi layer AlN/NbN	
					120	7	10		
					-	10	80		
					400	200	300		
					1.12	1.01	0.69		
358	199	437	2						

¹ 350 kHz, 1.1 μs

² 50:50 N/Kr

Figure 7: Sample 21/08/19, (a) High resolution SEM of ion milled X-section of SIS multilayer structure deposited on Ta. (b) EDX chemical mapping of the X-section.

Figure 8: Rutherford backscattering spectra of a niobium titanium nitride multilayer SIS structure deposited on sapphire (19/08/19). Spectra were collected for 2 MeV 4He+ and scattering angle of 165°. The angle of incidence was 0° (normal incidence).

As it can be seen the results predict over-stoichiometry of nitrogen level and a rich Ti level as compared to expected Nb level in all three NbTiN layers. This discrepancy and variation in the stoichiometry of NbTiN layers can be due to depth resolution within the chosen experimental condition. The future measurement will be performed at glancing incident where the depth resolution will be considerable increased. This will be further validated by performing a quantity EDS analysis. Analysis of superconducting properties of the SIS structures with SQUID magnetometry provides the results which are not directly related to their behaviour at the SRF condition. It requires applying AC, DC and RF testing methods where magnetic field is applied from one side of the film, similarly to the conditions at the real cavity. However, in the absence of the above setups, Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) was used to evaluate the SIS samples and the results are summarised in section 2.4.

Table 5: Layer thickness and composition determined by RBS.

Layer	Layer thickness (10 ¹⁵ at/cm ²)	Layer thickness (nm)	Nb	Ti	N	Al	O
1	227.7	52.6	20.1876	19.33	60.47	0	0
2	109.3	11.4	0	0	50	50	0
3	263.95	58.7	20.8	26.05	53.1	0	0
4	105.68	11.03	0	0	50	50	0
5	285.32	67.11	15.2	20.51	64.27	0	0
6	141.06	14.7	0	0	50	50	0
7	13510.8	2423.05	100	0	0	0	0

2.2 DEPOSITION AT SIEGEN

2.2.1 Deposition facility

A modified CemeCon CC800 industrial coating machine has been used to deposit all of the samples produced by University of Siegen as described in the previous reports. The substrate holder has been found to reach maximum temperatures of 300 °C. This is in contrast to the previous reported substrate temperature of 650 °C. The latter is the temperature measured at the heater itself and is found to be considerably lower due to the fact that the substrate holder has been modified for the ARIES project. To reach the aimed substrate temperature of 650 °C with the modified system a new heater system has been designed (see Figure 9) and is currently under construction.

During deposition of single layer films, the table is maintained in a stationary position, with the sample positioned directly opposite the target. With the deposition of SIS films, the table is rotated in order to ensure a homogeneous coating with uniform thickness. There are three magnetrons inside the deposition chamber, currently fitted with aluminium, titanium and niobium targets. The Nb target is situated in the centre of the three and is 100 × 88 mm² in size while the other two targets are 500 × 88 mm² in size. The niobium magnetron is powered by an ADL DC power supply but has the possibility of being used in HiPIMS operation as well. The targets can be concealed individually behind shutter doors, allowing for individual or multiple target deposition as well as target cleaning, without the risk of contamination. The layout of the chamber leads to a substrate to target distance of 55 mm. All of the NbN samples were deposited using Reactive DC Magnetron Sputtering (R-DCMS). Ar, Kr and N₂, were used during deposition.

Figure 9: Modified substrate holder system of the CC800 deposition tool. Substrate holder for ARIES samples in yellow and the new central heater visible between the two cylinders.

2.2.2 Sample Preparation

The main substrates used during the more recent study of NbN thin films were made from 1mm thick OFHC Cu, cut into a square shape with dimensions of 25 × 25 mm². A hole is drilled in one corner to facilitate hanging during the electropolishing process. In all coatings, a piece of Si wafer was used as a witness sample. The Cu and Si samples were positioned such that they both lie opposite to the trench of the target. The arrangement can be seen in Figure 10.

Based on the results detailed in ARIES Deliverable Report D15.1 [2], the Cu samples were prepared using a combination of mechanical polishing followed by a final electropolishing process. The electropolishing process used is similar to that detailed in D15.1. The sample is positioned at the anode and polished using a phosphoric acid (85%) and butanol mixture in a 3:2 volume ratio for 1

hour. This results in removal of $\sim 40 \mu\text{m}$ from the surface and leads to a mirror-like surface devoid of any scratches, inclusions or pitting.

Figure 10: Image of substrate holder fitted with Cu sample and Si witness sample (left) and image displaying the target setup of the coating system (right). The Nb target is positioned in the centre.

After loading the samples into the chamber, the chamber is baked for 8 hours at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to allow for conditioning of the chamber and outgassing of any components. The temperature is then lowered to the deposition temperature, which ensures no further outgassing during deposition. Prior to deposition, the system achieves a base pressure of 6×10^{-7} mbar at the required deposition temperature. The deposition pressure is maintained between 8×10^{-3} and 1.8×10^{-2} mbar. Just prior to deposition, the substrates are subjected to a MF etching process inside the coating chamber as a final surface treatment, and the Nb target is sputter cleaned for 5-10 minutes to ensure it is also cleaned of any possible contaminants which could influence the film quality.

In total, 30 System 2 (NbN) samples and 4 Superconductor-Insulator-Superconductor (SIS) coatings were deposited on the electropolished Cu substrates. The deposition parameters used for the NbN samples are summarised in Table 6.

Following the completion of the NbN single film optimisation process, a series of initial SIS coatings were deposited in the form of Cu/Nb/AlN/NbN by DC Magnetron Sputtering. The thickness of the Nb and AlN layers were held constant at $4 \mu\text{m}$ and 30 nm respectively, while the NbN layer was deposited in thicknesses of 150 nm, 200 nm and 250 nm, in order to investigate the effects of outer superconductor thickness on SIS performance. A single Nb layer sample was also deposited to investigate the performance of the single layer and compare it to the results of the SIS samples.

Table 6: Summary of NbN single layer samples and their deposition parameters

Sample ID	Pressure (mPa)	N ₂ %	Bias (V)	Cathode Power (W)	Substrate Temperature (°C)	Thickness (μm)
Nitrogen Percentage						
811	800	4	0	500	270	1.13
789	800	6	0	500	270	1.09
790	800	8	0	500	270	1.18
793	800	10	0	500	270	1.12
810	800	12	0	500	270	1.16
797	800	14	0	500	270	1.17
799	800	16	0	500	270	1.14
808	800	18	0	500	270	1.14
809	800	20	0	500	270	1.36
814	800	30	0	500	270	1.48
Bias						
821	800	10	25	500	270	1.22
815	800	10	50	500	270	1.15
820	800	10	75	500	270	1.13
816	800	10	100	500	270	1.2
817	800	10	150	500	270	1.17
818	800	10	200	500	270	1.34
819	800	10	300	500	270	1.37
Pressure						
822	600	10	0	500	270	1.16
823	1000	10	0	500	270	1.17
824	1400	10	0	500	270	1.09
825	1800	10	0	500	270	1.12
Optimised						
889	800	6	0	400	270	1.27
891	800	8	0	400	270	1.48
892	600	10	0	400	270	0.9
893	600	8	75	400	270	1.34
897	1200	8	0	400	290	1.34
898	1400	8	0	500	290	1.9
899	1400	8	75	500	290	1.06
900	1200	6	75	500	270	1.41
902	1200	8	50	400	270	1.12

The sample list and deposition parameters of the SIS films are summarised in Table 7. The NbN recipe from sample 897 was used for the NbN film of the SIS films, based on information gathered from SEM, XRD and AFM analysis, as no superconducting tests had been completed yet.

Table 7: Summary of SIS samples and their deposition parameters

Sample ID	Layer	Deposition Parameters					
		Material	Pressure (mPa)	Cathode Power (W)	Substrate Temperature (°C)	N ₂ %	Thickness (nm)
927, 931, 935, 937	1	Nb	800	400	290	0	4000
	2	AlN	600	3500	180	100	30
	3	NbN	1200	400	290	8	200, 200, 150, 250
941		Nb	800	400	290	0	4000

2.2.3 NbN film investigations

Three separate series of NbN films have been deposited, while adjusting only a single parameter within each series, and maintaining all others equal. The series investigated the effects of changing N₂ % (or N₂/Ar ratio change), the effects of increasing substrate bias and the effects of adjusting deposition pressure on the resulting film structure, NbN phase formation and superconducting properties. From initial experiments [3], we discovered that a high cathode power and low deposition pressure leads to the deposition of higher density films and thus samples in these investigations were coated at 500 W cathode power and 800 mPa unless otherwise stated.

Initial experiments sought to optimise the δ -NbN phase by adjusting the N₂/Ar ratio while maintaining the high cathode power and lower pressure. Most of the films deposited at this low pressure and high power displayed a silver coloured film, except the two samples deposited at 6 and 8 % which displayed a gold colour film. This indicates that multiple phases are present or the correct stoichiometry for δ -NbN was not achieved for most of the samples.

This is confirmed by XRD scans, displayed in Figure 11, which indicate an increasing presence of the hexagonal δ' -NbN phase with increasing N₂/Ar ratio, at this low pressure and high power. This is shown by the peak at 34.5°, slightly shifted from the relevant PDF card (00-014-0547) position of 34.87°. The δ -NbN phase is also identified using the peaks at 35.35° and 41.05° provided by PDF card 00-038-1155. The peaks however, are fairly broad, indicating a nano-crystalline structure, confirmed by SEM investigations. At lower N₂ %, samples display a δ (200) orientation. However, from 10 % N₂, the intensity of the δ' peak steadily increases and surpasses that of the δ phase peak. This is understandable, as the stoichiometry of the δ' phase is larger than that of the δ phase. Thus, when the N₂ % in the deposition chamber is increased, the likelihood of forming the δ' phase is higher. This also explains the change of film colour from light gold to silver. The hexagonal δ' phase also possesses larger average crystallite sizes than the δ phase, with sizes of roughly 15 nm compared to

5 nm, although both phases show an increase in crystallite size with increasing N₂ %. A significant peak shift is also present for the hexagonal phase in these samples, not present in the optimised samples presented later.

Figure 11: a) XRD patterns of samples deposited at different nitrogen percentages. Scans completed in Bragg-Brentano configuration Cu ($K\alpha$) radiation. b) XRD patterns of samples deposited at 10% N₂ with different pressure. Scans completed as in (a)

The films themselves display a relatively dense cross-sectional microstructure however the presence of some voids within the film is evident. Even so, there is good adhesion found between the NbN film and Cu substrate, with no evidence of voids between the film and the substrate or delamination. There is a lack of definitive structure to the films deposited at low N₂ %, however they become increasingly columnar with increasing N₂ %. The surface structure remains smooth and is constituted by collections of rounded grain formations which gives the surface a smeared look. This structure is similar for all films deposited in this series, regardless of N₂ %. This is showcased in Figure 12 (a-d). The cross section images were obtained through imaging the cleaved Si witness sample while the surface images were obtained from the film deposited onto electropolished Cu.

Figure 12: (a-d) SEM images of $N_2\%$ variation films. Figures (a) and (b) detail the cross section and surface of the 8% film while (c) and (d) detail the cross section and surface of the 18% film. (e-h) SEM images of sample 822, deposited at low pressure and sample 825, deposited at high pressure. Figures (e) and (f) display the cross section and surface of sample 822, while figures (g) and (h) display the cross section and surface of sample 825.

Figure 13: (a) Plot detailing the change in transition temperature and entry flux in parallel field, with increasing $N_2\%$. (b) Plot detailing the change in transition temperature and entry flux in parallel field, with increasing deposition pressure.

The transition temperature data and the first magnetic flux entry field, measured in a parallel field configuration, were provided by the Institute of Electrical Engineering (IEE) of the Slovak academy of Sciences (SAS) using a VSM attachment. The transition temperature data was obtained by monitoring the magnetic moment during cool-down of the sample through the transition temperature. A significant change in the signal marks the transition point from the normal to superconducting state. The results displayed in Figure 13 (a), indicate that the transition temperatures of these films are fairly consistent, around the 11 – 12 K mark, except for a low initial value at 6% and the slight dip at 18% N_2 . The entry flux is found to achieve a significant maximum of 130 Oe at 8% N_2 , falling off at higher and lower values of N_2 . Thus, optimised samples were centred around 6 – 10% N_2 .

The use of increasing substrate bias did not significantly influence the NbN phase formation. The films display the presence of both a hexagonal phase and the sought after δ -NbN, similar to what is

found with the 10 % N₂ sample. The microstructure of the films also didn't show a significant change other than to bring about a rounding to the peaks of the grains at higher bias levels > 200V.

The most apparent change seen with the NbN films is brought about by increasing the deposition pressure. As shown in Figure 14 (a), the colour of the film is observed to change from a silver to a more pronounced gold colour, which is synonymous with the superconducting δ -NbN phase.

As displayed in Figure 12 (e-h), at low deposition pressure, the film displays a relatively dense cross-sectional structure while the surface consists of rounded nano-crystalline grains. At higher deposition pressures (>1200 mPa), a pronounced columnar structure is observed in conjunction with larger, faceted grains on the surface. This change is related to a reduction in the mean free path of the sputtered atoms at higher pressures, leading to a lower surface diffusion rate of adatoms on the substrate. This coincides with an increase in surface roughness with increasing deposition pressure, measured with both an AFM and a CLSM. These results are displayed in Figure 14 (b). The presence of voids within the film are also more apparent in those deposited at high pressures relative to those deposited at low pressures.

Figure 14: Image of NbN film deposited at low pressure (left) and high pressure (right), displaying the change in colour experienced with an increase in deposition pressure. (b) Surface roughness of samples deposited at different deposition pressure studied using an AFM and a CLSM.

The XRD results, showcased in Figure 11 (b), also indicate a significant change with increasing deposition pressure. All films are identified as predominantly δ -NbN, however films transition from a (200) oriented film at low pressures towards a pronounced (111) oriented film at higher pressure. The presence of the hexagonal δ' phase is also found at intermediate pressures, indicated by the peak at 34.7° for the 1000 mPa and 1400 mPa samples. This phase is not present at the highest pressure of 1800 mPa. Average crystallite sizes are also found to increase with increasing pressure, from roughly 6 nm at 600 mPa to 36 nm at 1800 mPa.

The superconducting properties of these samples were again measured by the VSM at IEE and are displayed in Figure 13 (b). The transition temperature of these samples was found to increase with pressure to a maximum of 15.3 K at 1400 mPa and then decrease to 14 K at 1800 mPa. The entry

field is seen to decrease above 1000 mPa, peaking at 84 Oe at 1000 mPa. This decrease in the entry field value is related to the decrease in film density at higher pressures which leads to increased formation of oxynitrides ($\text{Nb}_x\text{N}_y\text{O}_{1-y}$) between the NbN grains. Based on this, the optimised samples were centered around 1000-1400 mPa.

Following these initial investigations, a final series of optimised samples were deposited, taking into account the results of the previous samples. The aim with these samples was to maximise the superconducting transition temperature by combining a higher deposition pressure, lower N_2 % and the application of a low bias to maintain a dense film in spite of the increased pressure. The list of samples is found in Table 6. All of these samples possess a gold film colour and columnar growth structure topped by a faceted peak on the film surface and achieved an average $T_c = 15 \pm 1$ K.

Two samples in this series (889 and 891) were deposited with the same conditions as samples 789 and 790 from the N_2 % study, except at a lower cathode power of 400 W instead of 500 W. This slight reduction in cathode power decreases the deposition rate, thereby allowing more time for the Nb and N_2 to react at the substrate, leading to better stoichiometry, and also allows more time for the adatoms to diffuse on the surface, leading to denser films. The results of this were significant. The films now deposited at 400 W display a denser, more columnar structure than those deposited at 500 W, as evidenced in Figure 15. The samples also display a larger, more faceted peak on the film surface while maintaining the uniformity present on the higher power samples. This change did not lead to a significant change in surface roughness however.

Figure 15: SEM images of sample 789, deposited at high cathode power and sample 889, deposited at low cathode power. Figures (a) and (b) display the cross section and surface of sample 789, while figures (c) and (d) display the cross section and surface of sample 889.

This reduction of cathode power also resulted in a noteworthy change in the XRD spectra. Both samples coated with a higher cathode power, possessed the highest peak intensity corresponding to the (200) δ -NbN phase, similar to that shown for the 6 % sample in Figure 13 (a). Both of these samples displayed a light gold colour. When coated at lower cathode power, the highest intensity peak switched to the (111) δ -NbN phase for both samples while also narrowing considerably, indicating an increase in crystallite size. This confirms the increased surface diffusion proposed

earlier. Furthermore, the hexagonal δ' -NbN phase is identified in sample 891, deposited with 8 % N₂. This points to an interplay between cathode power, deposition pressure and N₂ % in relation to NbN phase formation, and how these parameters affect the reaction rate between Nb and N at the substrate and the surface diffusion rate. These results are shown in Figure 16 (a).

Figure 16: (a) XRD patterns of sample 889 and 891. Scans completed in Bragg-Brentano configuration using Cu (K α) radiation. (b) XRD patterns of sample 897,898 and 899. Scans completed in Bragg-Brentano configuration using Cu (K α) radiation.

The samples deposited at lower cathode power also displayed a more intense gold colour compared to the higher cathode power samples. Correspondingly, the transition temperature of the samples coated at lower cathode power increased noticeably. This is shown in Table 8. The best performing samples were sample 897, 898 and 899. The methodology behind sample 897 and 899 is expanded upon here. Sample 897 was coated at a lower cathode power (400 W), an intermediate deposition pressure (1200 mPa) and an elevated substrate temperature (280 °C). This was in an attempt to produce the gold columnar film found at higher deposition pressures while increasing the density of the film at higher pressures by using lower cathode power.

Lower N₂ % was also used to decrease the likelihood of forming the δ' phase. This thinking proved to be successful as the XRD scans, presented in Figure 16 (b),

Table 8: Transition temperature change of samples deposited at different cathode power levels.

N ₂ %	Transition Temperature	
	High Cathode Power	Low Cathode Power
6	6.9	10
8	11.75	14

indicate a (111) oriented δ -NbN film with a very low presence δ' -NbN. As shown in Figure 17, the columnar nature of the structure was also enhanced while maintaining the film density. Analysis with an AFM indicates a low RMS surface roughness of $S_q = 6.36 \pm 0.42$ nm as well. The recipe for sample 897 was later used with the multilayer samples. Sample 898 and 899 were coated at 1400 mPa and 500 W, however multiple changes were made to the other deposition parameters to try and improve upon the performance of sample 824 from the pressure study. The N_2 % was decreased, to try and eradicate the presence of the δ' -NbN phase and the substrate temperature was increased to 280 °C. A higher substrate temperature increases the mobility of adatoms, thereby increasing the surface diffusion, resulting in improved film density. A 75 V substrate bias was also applied to sample 899 to increase the surface diffusion so as to improve the density of the film. As evidenced in Figure 16 (b), these changes were successful. Sample 898 shows no evidence of any δ' -NbN while the relative intensity between the δ -NbN/ δ' -NbN of sample 899 increased relative to sample 824, while also increasing absolute intensity of the δ -NbN phase. The average crystallite size of both samples also increased to ~50 nm.

Figure 17: SEM images of optimised samples 897, 898 and 899. Figures (a) and (b) refer to the cross section and surface of sample 897, figures (c) and (d) refer to sample 898 and figures (e) and (f) refer to sample 899.

Representative SEM images for sample 898 and 899 are displayed in Figure 17. In comparison to sample 824, the cross section of sample 898 still displays a distinctly columnar structure while that of sample 899 exhibits a visually decreased columnar structure. Improved film density is apparent for both of the samples. The application of a substrate bias is thus seen to decrease the columnar structure present at these higher deposition pressures. The surface roughness of both samples 898 and 899 was also decreased considerably compared to sample 824, down to $S_q = 7.39 \pm 2.34$ nm and $S_q = 14.05 \pm 2.32$ nm respectively. These improvements culminated in the highest transition temperature of all NbN samples for sample 899 ($T_c = 16$ K). This sample also achieved the highest entry field for these optimised samples of $B_{en} = 50$ Oe. The transition temperatures for sample 897 and 898 is not

accurately discernible but is expected to be in the region of 16 K, while both show a decreased $B_{en} \approx 20$ Oe. This is a further indication that a denser film results in better superconducting properties.

2.2.4 Developing NbN based SIS samples on copper

A series of single SIS films with a NbN/AlN/Nb structure were also deposited onto Cu substrates. This structure is shown in Figure 18. The AlN recipe was developed as part of a separate study, but still utilised DCMS so that the sample did not require removal from the deposition chamber in between coatings. The NbN recipe used for the SIS films was chosen based on the results from the optimised samples. Thus, the recipe for sample 897 was chosen. Four SIS film samples were deposited with varying NbN thickness, based on the work by Kubo [17]. The deposited NbN layer thicknesses were 150, 200 and 250 nm, while the Nb and AlN thicknesses were maintained at 4.5 μm and 30 nm respectively. Between each coating run, a period of two hours was added to allow for the substrate to stabilise at the respective layer's deposition temperature. The pre-treatment of the substrate was the same as that used for the single layer NbN films. A single Nb layer was also deposited on a Cu substrate using the same conditions as the base layer of the SIS film for the purpose of superconducting performance comparison.

Figure 18: DCMS deposited SIS film structure

The homogeneity of the thickness of the individual films which constitute a SIS film are important to ensuring optimum performance. When coating with the substrate holder in a stationary position, a thickness gradient exists across the samples. In order to avoid this with the SIS films, the substrate holder is set to rotate during the deposition of the AlN and NbN films. The deposition rate for this rotating deposition was also calibrated prior to SIS film deposition. An initial SIS film trial with a thin Nb layer was completed on Si to better understand the growth of the SIS layers on one another and to fine tune the process. An SEM image of this film, including layer thicknesses, is displayed in Figure 19. It is clear that the NbN layer structure is similar to what was achieved for the single layer NbN sample (897) that this recipe is derived from. The different films also present a well-connected interface with no visible voided regions. FIB cuts were completed on selected SIS samples to better understand their structure, with the results presented in Figure 20 (a) and (b). From (a) we can see that the interface between the Cu substrate and the Nb film is plagued by voids. Further investigations of other samples provided evidence of similar events as well as film delamination. It is evident from (b) that the AlN and NbN layers have a homogeneous thickness across the entire surface, due to the rotation of the sample during coating. It is also apparent that the Nb film surface is considerably rougher than the Cu surface.

Figure 19: SEM image of pre-trial of sample 927 deposited on Si with a minimal thickness Nb (30nm) base layer.

Figure 20: SEM images detailing a) FIB cut through full thickness of sample 927. b) Zoomed in image of SIS structure of sample 927.

Figure 21: Representative SEM images of the surface of (Left) sample 927 and (Right) sample 935 indicating the difference in density of the two surfaces.

Figure 22: SEM images of (a) surface of single Nb layer used in SIS films and (b) surface of single NbN layer used in SIS film.

The roughness values, measured by AFM, for the samples coated with SIS films (927-937), the pure Nb film (941), the Nb + AlN film (942) and the single NbN layer film (897) are shown in Table 9

Table 9: Comparing surface roughness of SIS film, pure Nb film, Nb+AlN film and pure NbN film.

Sample	927	931	935	937	941	942	897
(nm)	12.79 2.49	13.16 1.61	15.74 1.22	13 2.15	19.38 4.33	15.79 1.7	6.36 0.42

Of the SIS films, sample 927 has the lowest surface roughness, however the difference between the SIS film samples is small. It is most likely due to the gaps present between grain structures on samples 931, 935 and 937. The results indicate that the SIS films possess a significantly rougher surface

compared to that of the individual NbN layer which they are based on. A further two additional samples, one coated with the same Nb layer as the SIS films and one coated with the Nb layer and the AlN layer, have been prepared and analysed to investigate this. The results point to a direct influence of the Nb layer on the resultant SIS film surface roughness.

Further inspections of SEM images of the SIS film surfaces, presented in Figure 21, indicate a distinct difference between sample 927 and the rest of the samples. Sample 927 displays a dense film surface while the rest of the samples, which have a similar surface to sample 935, show evidence of gaps between the different grain structures. This leads to an inhomogeneous shielding of the underlying Nb layer. This is believed to be due to the inhomogeneous growth of the underlying Nb.

The surfaces of the single layer NbN films, presented earlier, consisted of homogeneously deposited layers whereas the surfaces of the SIS films present a multitude of different grain structures and orientations. It is evident that the nanoscale NbN grains themselves are still homogeneously grown on the surface of the Nb layer, however the overall surface structure is vastly different. This surface is determined by the structure of the Nb layer below. Therefore, the resultant surface layer structure, and its effectiveness as a shielding layer, is determined by the underlying Nb layer. This difference is visible in the comparison between the single Nb layer used in the SIS films and the NbN layer used in the SIS films presented in Figure 22.

The XRD patterns for sample 897, the NbN film which the SIS films utilise, and sample 927, the best performing SIS film are shown in Figure 23. The results for the NbN layer used in the SIS film are consistent with what was measured with the single NbN layer film of sample 897. Once more, the film is characterised by a high intensity (111) δ -NbN peak at 35.4° as well as the presence of a secondary δ' -NbN peak at 34.6°. The peak for the AlN layer is indiscernible from the XRD patterns however, due to its low relative thickness and its positioning relative to the NbN peaks. The main peak present in the scan of sample 927 is that of the Nb layer, identified by the peak at 38.45°.

2.3 IMPROVEMENT OF Nb/Cu ADHESION AND INCREASE OF Nb CRYSTAL SIZE BY LASER RADIATION

Adhesion of Nb thin film to Cu substrate and size of Nb crystal grains for RF cavities were studied depending on laser intensity and dose. Structures of Nb/Cu, obtained by magnetron sputtering with 500 °C (Nr.1) and 700 °C (Nr.2) deposition temperature, were irradiated by pulsed Nd:YAG laser.

Figure 23: XRD patterns of single layer sample 897 and ML sample 927. Sample 927 is coated using the same recipe as 897. Scans completed in Bragg-Brentano configuration Cu ($K\alpha$) radiation.

Four areas, irradiated with doses $D_1 = 5.6 \times 10^{20}$, $D_2 = 8.8 \times 10^{20}$, $D_3 = 1.76 \times 10^{21}$ and $D_4 = 1.76 \times 10^{22}$ phot/cm², were studied. Delamination was investigated by scratching method using conical diamond indenter with force increased from 10 mN to 3.0 N. Characterization of the structure before and after the irradiation was performed using an optical microscope, AFM, SEM and XRD. Comparing with the non-irradiated area, the critical delamination force increased by 10% for sample Nr.2 and by 36% for sample Nr.1 at laser doses D_2 and D_4 , respectively. It means that Nb coating layer of sample Nr. 1 is better than that of sample Nr.2. The decrease of average roughness of Nb layer by an order of magnitude was observed after the laser irradiation. The improvement of the structure adhesion was also observed and explained by the diffusion of Nb atoms into Cu through dislocations. The increase of Nb crystallites size from 20 to 35 nm was calculated using XRD data.

The samples were irradiated by Q-switched pulsed Nd:YAG laser (model: NL301G, produced by Ekspla (Lithuania)) with the following parameters: fundamental wavelength 1064 nm, pulse duration 6 ns, range of intensities from 140.0 to 320.0 MW/cm² (at lower laser intensity, than 140.0 MW/cm² no changes of structural properties were observed), repetition rate of 10 Hz, beam profile "Hat-Top", beam diameter 1.0 mm. Scanning of the laser beam was performed normally to the Nb/Cu surface with the speed of 1.0 mm/s. The irradiation of the samples was carried out at room temperature in argon atmosphere to prevent oxidation. Four areas of the structure were irradiated with constant intensity $I = 200.0$ MW/cm² and different doses: $D_1 = 5.6 \times 10^{20}$ phot/cm²; $D_2 = 8.8 \times 10^{20}$ phot/cm²; $D_3 = 1.76 \times 10^{21}$ phot/cm²; $D_4 = 1.76 \times 10^{22}$ phot/cm². Such intensity of the laser radiation was chosen according to the intensity-dependent study of morphology by scanning electron microscope (SEM) method. At intensity between 170 and 253 MW/cm², the laser induced-polishing of Nb layer takes place and the surface becomes smoother – see

Figure 24 shows the FESEM images of Nb/Cu sample Nr.1 before (a) and after irradiation by Nd:YAG laser with intensities: $I_1 = 140 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (b), $I_2 = 170 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (c), $I_3 = 253 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (d) and $I_4 = 320 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (e). One can see that before the laser irradiation (Fig. 1a) there are grains with sharp edges and typical sizes from 0.5 to $2 \mu\text{m}$. These sharp edges are somewhat smoothen after the laser irradiation at the smallest intensity I_1 (Fig. 1b). That indicates that melting of Nb surface starts

at intensity near $I_1 = 140 \text{ MW/cm}^2$. Further increasing of the laser intensity leads to an evident surface melting. It causes a fusion of grains (Figs. 1c and 1d). As a result, the surface roughness has decreased significantly. The surface became almost completely flat and smooth after the irradiation with the largest laser intensity $I_4 = 320 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (Fig. 1e). However, some cracks appeared at intensities $I \geq I_2$. These can be interpreted as solidification cracks [18, 19], observed in many materials due to a rapid solidification of the liquid phase after irradiation by a short laser pulse.

Figure 24: FESEM images of Nb/Cu sample Nr.1 before the irradiation (a) and after the irradiation by Nd:YAG laser with intensities $I_1 = 140 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (b), $I_2 = 170 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (c), $I_3 = 253 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (d) and $I_4 = 320 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (e).

Figure 25: XRD pattern of Nb on Cu substrate of sample Nr.1 before and after the irradiation by Nd:YAG laser at intensity $I = 200 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.

In addition, some holes were observed on the cracks at the largest intensities I_3 and I_4 , pointing to a possible boiling, which occurs under a solid Nb layer. This phenomenon is known as the “lid effect” [20]. However, the Cu boiling temperature $T_b^{Cu} = 2835 \text{ K}$ exceeds the melting temperature of crystalline Nb, which is $T_m^{Nb} = 2741 \text{ K}$, and polycrystalline Nb should have an even lower melting temperature. Hence, it is more likely that ejection of rapidly expanding molten Cu takes place through the holes in the solid Nb layer.

Figure 26: The 3D AFM images of Nb/Cu sample Nr.1: non-irradiated (a) and irradiated by Nd:YAG laser at intensity $I = 200.0 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ (b). The Nb surface roughness R_a is 7.6 nm for the non-irradiated sample and 0.5 nm – for the irradiated one.

The XRD patterns of the same sample before and after the irradiation by Nd:YAG laser are shown in Figure 25. Using the Scherrer equation and XRD data, it was found that the size of Nb crystallites increased from 20 to 35 nm after the laser irradiation. A decrease of crystal lattice constant from 3.370 to 3.285 Å was observed, which is, probably, caused by the laser-induced mechanical compressive stress. The surface roughness was also studied with AFM. The AFM images of sample Nr.1 before the irradiation and after the irradiation with the intensity $I = 200.0 \text{ MW/cm}^2$ are presented in Figure 26. These images show a very significant reduction of the Nb surface roughness R_a from 7.6 nm to 0.5 nm due to the irradiation. This smoothening effect is qualitatively the same as observed in Fig. 1. However, Figure 26 shows a much smaller surface area without cracks seen in

Figure 24.

The combination of scratch test results of non-irradiated (Figure 27a, b) and irradiated with doses D_2 and D_4 (Figure 27c, d) sample Nr.2 shows that the coating has defects, such as areas of coating, which have not adhered with the copper base. After high irradiation dose (D_4), these areas of the coating were peeled off, but areas, which were adhered with the base, were not delaminated during the scratch

test. So, summarizing the results of sample Nr.2, one can say that the laser irradiation not only affects the adhesion of the coating, but also increases the hardness of the surface. The least favourable results were obtained for Nb/Cu structure of sample Nr.2 after the laser irradiation with dose D_4 . In this case, the surface was already delaminated just after the laser treatment (see Figure 27d).

Figure 27: Optical microscope images of Nb/Cu structure of sample Nr.2: surface view (a) before scratch test and irradiation, (b) after scratch test before irradiation and (c, d) after the irradiation by laser with doses D_2 and D_4 , respectively, followed by scratch test.

An indenter penetration depth and a residual depth for sample Nr.2 during the scratch test depends on the laser irradiation dose. The minimal indentation depth is $9.0 \mu\text{m}$ for D_2 and the maximal one is $12.6 \mu\text{m}$ for the non-irradiated area. It means that the hardness of the structure was increased after the laser irradiation. Critical delamination force is maximal for the laser dose D_2 , and it is increased by 10% as compared with the non-irradiated area.

The same scratch tests have been performed for sample Nr.1 (Figure 28). The critical delamination force depending on the laser irradiation dose is shown in Figure 29.

It was found that, for sample Nr.1, this force increases with the irradiation dose. The maximal effect was observed for the dose D_4 , where the delamination force increased by 36% as compared with the non-irradiated area. The indentation depth depending on the irradiation dose is shown in Figure 30. Its lowest measured value of $8.5 \mu\text{m}$ corresponds to the laser dose D_2 and the highest value of 10.84

μm corresponds to the non-irradiated area. That means that thin Nb film of sample Nr.1 is better than that of sample Nr.2 because the delamination force and the hardness is increased more after the laser irradiation. This increase in the surface hardness is very likely related to the growth of the size of Nb crystals, as well as to their coalescence.

Figure 28: Optical microscope images of Nb/Cu structure of sample Nr.1: (a) before irradiation and (b) after the irradiation by laser with D4. Yellow arrows show delaminated Nb from Cu.

Figure 29: Critical force for the coating delamination of sample Nr.1 depending on the laser doses: D₁, D₂, D₃, D₄.

Figure 30: The maximal depth of indentation (scratch), denoted as Max Pd, of sample Nr.1 when load was 3N, and the difference ΔPd between the Max Pd and the Rd (residual depth). The quantity ΔPd shows how much the surface relaxes after the indentation.

In a nutshell: The properties of non-irradiated and laser-irradiated Nb/Cu structure were studied. It has been demonstrated that:

- The adhesion of Nb film can be improved: the critical delamination force for irradiated Nb/Cu structure is increased after the laser dose by maximally 36%.
- The laser irradiation of Nb/Cu structure leads to a decrease of average surface roughness from 7.6 to 0.5 nm, according to AFM results.
- The crystalline size in Nb layer is increased by 20% after the irradiation of the structure by Nd:YAG laser at the intensity $I = 200 \text{ MW/cm}^2$.
- The experimentally observed holes on the Nb surface could be, eventually, explained by the “lid-effect” – the explosive ejection of molten Cu through broken solid Nb layer.

2.4 DC SUPERCONDUCTIVITY EVALUATION AT IEE

Superconducting parameters were determined on flat samples with single superconducting layer as well as with multiple superconducting layers, prepared at the deposition facilities of the work-package partners.

Approximately 100 samples in total were characterised at IEE during the year 3 of the project. The sample sets included samples with several superconducting layers – the Multilayer samples. These were most often of the Superconductor-Insulator-Superconductor (SIS) layer architecture, with one or several repetitions of the Insulator-Superconductor layer sequence. Samples comprising a single superconducting layer of Nb on Cu substrate were tested as well, prepared using the HiPIMS (High Power Impulse Magnetron Sputtering) deposition method. Samples were deposited mostly on Cu substrates, part of the multilayer samples also on Sapphire and Ta substrates and some were prepared as self-supported (SS) samples as well.

The characterisation consisted in measurements of the virgin DC magnetization curves and magnetization loops on small measurement samples of approximately 2 mm × 2 mm. For samples deposited on Cu substrates these measurement samples were cut with the help of a laboratory cut-off machine (saw) using a SiC cut-off disc. Measurement samples from the Sapphire (Sapp) substrate samples were prepared by cleaving and from the Ta substrate samples by cutting with scissors, as the Ta substrates were relatively thin (tape-like) and it was very complicated to fix them on a supporting plate for cutting. It turned out, however, that practically all the Ta substrate measurement samples were damaged due to the cutting (bent edges, very probably cracks in the film) and the results obtained on the Ta substrate samples were thus not considered. The self-supported samples were very carefully attached onto a piece of an adhesive Kapton tape and subsequently the 2 mm × 2 mm measurement samples were cut with scissors. Although the film is in principle quite prone to damage during this procedure as well, the results measured on the self-supported samples were comparable to the Cu substrate samples.

Figure 31: Illustration of determination of the characteristic field H_{en} from the virgin magnetization curves.

In the magnetization measurements, the component of the magnetic moment (m) of the sample parallel to the external applied magnetic field H was measured, using the Vibrating Sample Magnetometer (VSM) option of the commercial PPMS system (model 6000) from Quantum Design Inc. The magnetic moment m was measured in dependence on monotonically increasing (or decreasing) applied field H , recording the so-called magnetization curves $m(H)$. The magnetization curves were measured on samples cooled down below T_c in zero applied magnetic field (zero-field-cooled conditions, ZFC). The external magnetic field was applied parallel to the flat face of the samples. The main characteristic determined from the magnetization curves is the so-called first flux entry field H_{en} . It is the applied field at which the magnetic flux starts entering the sample's volume. It was detected as the field at which the virgin magnetization curve starts to deviate from the linear dependence that the virgin curve follows in the initial part starting from the zero applied field, as schematically illustrated in Figure 31. The field H_{en} was determined employing 2% relative difference criterion, i.e. as the applied field at which the relative difference between the virgin magnetization curve and the initial linear trend reaches 2%. The H_{en} is proportional to the first (lower) critical field B_{c1} through a geometrical constant that depends on the dimensions of the sample. In the case of the majority of the sapphire substrate samples the flux jumps occurring at relatively low applied fields hindered reliable H_{en} determination.

The first magnetic flux entry fields of all relevant samples deposited on Cu substrate tested since the beginning of the project are summarized in Figure 32. As can be seen, both the multilayer SIS and the simple SIS structures have the potential of reaching relatively high H_{en} values, close or above 50 mT. This is above the best typical values determined for the simple Nb/Cu samples deposited using

the standard DC magnetron sputtering, however, some of the multilayer samples show only very low H_{en} values. These pronounced differences between otherwise similar or almost identical samples could most probably be ascribed to different surface quality of the final (top) layer of the structure, especially in terms of occurrence of “sharp” surface defects or irregularities. The SEM images reported above show for example much bigger and sharper irregularities on the NbN surface of the 935 sample than for the 927 and the H_{en} determined for the 935 is indeed considerably smaller. Such defects present points of local field enhancement and can promote the flux penetration into the superconducting layer at considerably lower applied fields. The surface quality effects could also play a role in the observed somewhat different performance of the four Nb₃Sn/Cu samples tested earlier.

Magnetization measurements in the VSM are not ideal for characterisation of multilayer superconducting films. During the measurement, the whole sample is immersed in the applied homogeneous magnetic field and in principle it would thus be possible the magnetic flux would start to enter through the Cu/Nb interface (substrate side) at a smaller applied field than from the top multilayer interface. If this would be the case we should, however, see more or less the same H_{en} for all samples in one set, as the substrate preparation and Nb deposition procedure was the same for all samples in the set. The notable differences in H_{en} between the samples of one set indicate the start of magnetic flux penetration at the top of the SIS (multilayer) structure.

Very encouraging are the relatively high and reproducible H_{en} values of the Nb/Cu samples deposited using the HiPIMS method. The values are well above the best typical values determined for the standardly deposited Nb/Cu samples. The variations of H_{en} between the samples are understandable as the samples presented were part of an optimisation study where the deposition parameters, like the cathode power, deposition pressure and pulse length, varied in certain range.

2.5 EXPLORING EVALUATION OF SUPERCONDUCTING FILMS WITH PHOTO- AND THERMOSTIMULATED EXOELECTRON EMISSION SPECTRA AT RTU

Another study performed at RTU aimed to explore the possibility of using photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission to superconducting thin film evaluation. The analysis of results was performed on samples obtained from the first set of 14 samples of Nb films, deposited by ARIES project partners on the Cu substrates, which were initially pre-processed by different methods. No relationships found between parameters of photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission spectra and Cu substrate preparation method. No correlation was found between photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission and surface roughness of Cu substrate and deposited Nb layers, as well as photo- and thermostimulated exoelectron emission and magnetic characteristic of the Nb films. The main conclusion was that this method is not suitable in present stay for characterising superconducting thin films.

Figure 32: Comparison of the H_{en} (2% criterion) of all relevant Cu substrate samples tested since the Y1. The type of samples in the respective set is indicated by the blue-font labels.

3. Study of SC thin films on QPR samples

3.1 QPR SAMPLE

The main purpose of this work is to perform field measurements at realistic radio-frequencies, (in the Gigahertz range) on flat sheet-samples for which the manufacturing procedure was optimized in the previous phase. The workflow is schematically shown in Figure 33. After manufacture at Research Instruments, the QPR samples were sent to INFN for surface finishing on a lathe and two different chemical polishing steps. Sample were passed to USI and STFC for Nb coating and finally back to HZB for the RF tests.

Figure 33: Workflow of applying small sample procedures to QPR samples.

3.1.1 QPR sample manufacturing

A total of 10 samples (yellow) to fit the quadrupole resonator were manufactured at Research Instruments, 5 made from bulk Nb, and 5 of a copper disc weld into a cylindrical Nb pipe. The actual area that is being exposed to the RF field, and that is thus being measured, is the outside face of the cylinder. In mounted state, the sample is located inside the resonator chamber underneath the pole shoes of the resonator rods. The inside of the samples serves as a separate chamber and is equipped with threaded fixtures for heaters and temperature sensors for calorimetric measurements.

Figure 34: Quadrupole resonator: Illustration of sample placement and features.

3.1.2 Sample case

For the shipment of samples, a dedicated chamber has been designed and manufactured. It consists of ISO-KF160 standard pieces, equipped with suitable fixtures for the samples, and an evacuation manifold, see Figure 35. It allows to transport the QPR samples under clean room conditions in vacuum or arbitrary atmospheres. For future sample treatment steps, i.e. Laser irradiation at Riga University, a glass window can be used as the top lid. By using such a glass window, the laser treatments can be performed even if the partner institute does not have the required clean-room infrastructure.

Figure 35: Transport box for shipment of samples to laser treatment facility at U Riga. Samples are shipped under clean atmosphere and do not need to be opened at the laser treatment facility.

3.2 DEVELOPING QPR SAMPLE POLISHING

Following the results obtained from D15.1 on planar samples [2], two polishing techniques were adapted to the QPR samples treatment: chemical polishing (SUBU5) and electropolishing. Before proceeding with the polishing treatments, several experiments were carried out, to solve some problems that had to be faced, such as: enormous pitting, machining lines, point, defects, uniformity, oxidations, quantity of material removed and others. A dummy QPR sample (QPR B-0) was used for initial test treatments to define the polishing protocol.

A total of five Cu/Nb QPR samples (B-1 - B-5) were polished at LNL with two different techniques: three of them with SUBU (B-1, B-2, B-5) and two of them with electropolishing (B-3, B-4). A mechanical polishing was performed prior to the chemical or the electrochemical polishing for all five QPRs.

3.2.1 Mechanical Polishing

Due to the high roughness of the QPR Cu plate with $R_a \sim 1.6 \mu\text{m}$, $R_z \sim 12 \mu\text{m}$, see Figure 36 (a), it was decided to apply the mechanical polishing before the chemical and electrochemical processes. The planar geometry allows the usage of lathe machining and prevents surface contamination by abrasive media as normally happens in cavities with centrifugal barrel, tumbling or grinding polishings. As a cooling fluid deionized water or isopropyl alcohol were used in order to avoid Nb surface contaminations by oils normally which are normally used in lathe machining.

The QPR B-0 was used for initial test treatments to find and solve possible problems during processing. Holdings of the QPR samples initially were done directly with Lathe machine equipment - mandrel. After some tests, this approach was changed and a plastic holder was used, see Figure 37. This configuration has got two main advantages: it prevents scratching of Nb walls and helps to center correctly the QPR on the lathe. However, the construction of the QPR presents small alignment imperfections and this causes a slightly off-axis rotation of the QPR which complicates the processing of the copper plate. Due to the misalignment, the polishing does not take place uniformly and repetition of machining is necessary to obtain a uniform machine surface polishing.

The final polishing results are directly correlated to the mechanical polishing surface. During our tests we noted an increasement of pitting produced during chemical and electrochemical polishing, due to an amount of sticked bubbles of oxygen in the zone in which "lathe scratches" are more visible. Several tests proved that 90 microns is the minimum removal thickness for each step that produces a low roughness surface. Lathe speed rotation, as well, plays a significant role: low speed increases the quality of the surface, see Figure 38.

The presence of the electron beam welding on the surface limits the removal material. We consider 200 microns a safety limit not to overcome. For a good mechanical polishing it is necessary to remove a minimum of 90 microns.

Figure 36: On the left: milling machining surface appearance of QPRs sample as received at LNL. On the right B-0 sample after lathe mechanical polishing at LNL

Figure 37: QPR mounted directly on the mandrel (left) and with a plastic support (right).

Figure 38: Non uniform machining across the radius.

3.2.2 Chemical Polishing

Chemical polishing with a SUBU5 [7] was used. This method has proven numerous times as a good and fast recipe to polish Copper (decrease roughness of the surface). The solution is composed of two main chemicals: Sulfamic acid (5 g/l) and n-Butanol (50 ml/l) with two additional: Ammonium Citrate (1 g/l) and Hydrogen Peroxide (50 ml/l). SUBU polishing requires immersing of samples into hot (72-73°C) solution under constant agitation. Depending on the ratio volume of the solution/copper surface area, the removal rate can vary from about 1 to 5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{min}$. Standard time of treatment (5 min) can be decreased or prolonged depending on the aim, such as: a good surface does not require too much time (typically after EP), longer exposing can even decrease the reflectivity; instead, if initial roughness is high, longer exposing can only be useful. Absence of a good motion inside the solution, can lead to pitting, such situations can require closer look at the processing.

A successful application of SUBU5 polishing technique on planar samples [2, 9] was relatively simple. Even though the geometry and the area of Cu surface remain similar, large volume and weight of QPR samples increase the complexity of the polishing procedure. This time it was needed to take into account the cooling down of the solution due to the large weight of QPR. A large volume of SUBU solution and a pre-heating of the sample was mandatory to reduce this issue. We also had to deal with unexpected more pitting occurring, that was due to the described earlier problem of mechanical polishing.

Figure 39: Vertical (left) and horizontal (right) positioning of QPR sample during SUBU treatment.

Positioning. At first, we treated the QPR B-0 sample in vertical position, where the Cu plate was inserted first into the solution with continuous agitation on the maximum speed of the magnetic stirrer. Unfortunately, this configuration produced hard pitting, since the agitation was not enough to prevent sticking of Oxygen bubbles to the Cu surface. Manual wiggling of the sample did not improve the surface quality. On the contrary, processing of the QPR in horizontal position (see. Figure 39) prevents Oxygen bubbles sticking producing a high quality and low roughness surface. Agitation of the solution was maintained by a magnetic stirrer and manual up and down movements of the QPR during processing.

Oxidation. After SUBU treatment, a nanometer scale passivation layer is grown to prevent copper oxidation using a solution of Sulfamic acid. This layer is easily decomposed under vacuum conditions, prior to the coating process. The protocol of passivation requires immediate immersing of the sample after SUBU treatment. This protocol worked reliably for planar samples, while for QPR

some stains of oxidation occurred at first in preliminary trials. The cause of the oxidations and stains are the exposure of copper surface to the air, partially covered by the hot solution of SUBU. In such conditions few seconds are enough to damage the surface. The issue was solved by moving directly the QPR from the SUBU5 bath to the Sulfamic Acid bath without emptying the SUBU5 solution, which remains trapped in the QPR cavity, when it is treated in horizontal position. In case of failure, the sample is re-polished for 1 minute in SUBU5 solution and the passivation process is repeated. In Figure 40 the effect of a SUBU5 treatment is illustrated.

Figure 40: QPR B-5 surfaces overview before (left) and after (right) SUBU5 treatment.

Finally, the complete SUBU5 polishing protocol of QPR samples is reported below:

1. Ultrasound degreasing in GP1740 soap (NGL) for 1 hour at 40 °C.
2. Ultrasound cleaning in deionized water for 30 min.
3. Distilled water and Ethanol rinsing, drying with Nitrogen gun.
4. Mounting Nb wire across the Nb body for SUBU polishing.
5. Preheating in distilled water of the QPR up to ~ 60 °C.
6. SUBU5 polishing, at 72–73 °C, for 4–7 min, with magnetic agitation and manual up and down movements. Constant visual observation.
7. Instant transportation of QPR samples into ambient temperature solution of Sulfamic acid (10 g/l), 3–5 min. Constant visual observation.
8. Ultrasonic cleaning in deionized water for 20 minutes. Two times solutions are changed.
9. Under wet conditions of QPR, mounting wires are being carefully disassembled.
10. High Pressure Rinsing, at 120 atm, 2 minutes.
11. Deionized water rinsing, Ethanol rinsing and Nitrogen drying.
12. Immediate transportation of the QPR into a stainless steel transporting chamber.

3.2.3 Electrochemical Polishing

Electropolishing is a well-studied and used technique that can smooth the surface to the lowest values of roughness. Conventional electropolishing is done in viscous solutions of acids. Two electrodes are immersed inside the solution, and connected to the power supply. The anode, positive charged electrode, is the electrode polished under these conditions. It is also required for the opposite electrode to be the same shape as the anode sample, and to have a relatively low distance of 2-4 cm between the electrodes. In deliverable 15.1 [2] the use of this technique on ARIES planar samples is reported, in which low roughness values and high reflectivity were obtained. The same protocol was used for QPR samples:

1. Ultrasound degreasing in GP1740 soap (NGL) for 1 hour at 40 °C.
2. Ultrasound cleaning in deionized water for 30 min.
3. Deionized water and Ethanol rinsing, drying with Nitrogen gun.
4. Mounting Nb wire onto the flange of QPR sample.
5. Electropolishing in Phosphoric acid:n-Butanol = 3:2 v.r. , at 40 °C for 40–60 minutes.
6. Fast rinsing with distilled water.
7. Ultrasonic cleaning in Deionized water for 20 minutes. Two times solutions are changed.
8. Under wet conditions of QPR, mounting wires are being carefully disassembled.
9. High Pressure Rinsing, at 120 atm, 2 minutes.
10. Deionized water rinsing, Ethanol rinsing and Nitrogen drying.
11. Immediate transportation of the QPR into a stainless steel transporting chamber.

The main topics on adjustments of the polishing protocol to QPR samples treatment were: positioning of the QPR, temperature, oxidations.

Positioning. The main draft of the possible positions included: horizontal, vertical with Cu plate on the top, vertical with Cu plate on the bottom, see Figure 41. Eventually, vertical positioning of the Cu plate to the top (see Figure 41, middle) was the most promising configuration. Other positions had major problems, such as: horizontal: non uniform, wavy surface of Cu, due to the constant lowering of viscous layer during EP, possible line texturing (similar to the planar samples defects we had); vertical with Cu plate on the bottom: pitting and severe decrease of the current due to the massive bubbles of Hydrogen and Oxygen that is blocking the surface of Cu.

Temperature. The final vertical position of the QPR sample had a minor drawback: since the viscous layer during processing was not removed from the surface, the more it grows, the less current can pass through the low-conducting layer. Conventional ways to increase mass-exchange processes are floating, agitation and pumping. Pumping and magnetic stirrer agitation was tested with the result of wavy (non-uniform appearing) surfaces. After that, it was decided to simply increase temperature, decreasing the viscosity of the solution, which is useful as well, from the point of view of pitting prevention.

Figure 41: Overview of the possible QPR positions tested: horizontal (left), vertical Cu plate up (middle), vertical Cu plate down (right).

Oxidations. This problem is a rare situation in electropolishing processes. However, in the situation with two joint metals of different nature it could appear. Preliminary test and B-3 sample didn't show any signs of oxidation, but a strong gold color of the cylindrical walls on sample B-4 was an indication that niobium anodization had occurred. Six hours in HF solution at 5% remove completely the Nb oxide, but this longer exposure decreased even the reflectivity of copper surfaces, which was retreated for a second time. The different behaviour between the two QPRs is caused by the use of EP's automatic program developed at LNL, which follows the plateau of the polishing process by rastering different potentials. The issue was solved by working in manual mode and maintaining the process voltage below 2.2 V.

3.2.4 Summary of Treatments done

In Table 10 the treatments performed on the 5 copper-embedded QPR samples are summarized.

3.3 DEPOSITION ON QPR SAMPLES

The QPR samples have been and are being deposited at INFN, Siegen and STFC. The effort at three partner's laboratories was put on significant modification of the existing facilities at INFN (Figure 2-8) and Siegen (Figure 2-9) or designing and building a new facility at STFC (Figure 2-10). These facilities are in operation now, ongoing tests with mock samples are essential for optimising all deposition parameters. As soon as any of these facilities is ready for the real QPR sample, the samples will be sent for deposition, and then for the QPR test at HZB and CERN.

Table 10: Summarizing table on mechanical and chemical treatments done onto QPR samples.

#	QPR Sample	Protocol	Sent to deposit	Notes
1	B-1	1. Lathe (650 μm) 2. SUBU (6 μm) 3. Passivation 4. HPR	STFC	Due to severe mechanical layer removal, after deposition, Cu plate cracked. B-1 is substituted by the B-5 sample.
2	B-2	1. Lathe (50 μm) 2. SUBU (7 μm) 3. Passivation 4. HPR	SIEGEN	Successfully measured at HZB
3	B-3	1. Lathe (129 μm) 2. EP (17 μm) 3. Passivation 4. HPR	SIEGEN	Successfully measured at HZB
4	B-4	1. Lathe (175 μm) 2. EP (12 μm) 3. Passivation 4. HPR	STFC	Successfully measured at HZB
5	B-5	1. Lathe (45 μm) 2. SUBU (6 μm) 3. Passivation 4. HPR	STFC	Successfully measured at HZB

3.3.1 Deposition system at STFC

A dedicated deposition system was built and placed in a portable ISO 5 clean room. The system is comprised of RGA to monitor the vacuum quality at all stages, retractable 3 inch magnetron and view port for observing the surface of the QPR. The system is shown in Figure 42.

Figure 42: A mock QPR sample (left) and its coating in a new facility at STFC (right).

For the deposition procedure, the QPR sample was mounted onto the dedicated chamber under a portable cleanroom environment. In there, the chamber was baked for 48 hours at 150 °C. The temperature of the QPR was then gradually increased to 650 °C to a pre-set value (visual observation until it just started to Glow RED). Here, a degassing of massive excess Hydrogen was allowed for 24 hours. The following deposition time was set for 5 hours. After deposition, the QPR sample was cooled down over 12 hours. The deposition parameters for both SUBU and EP prepared QPR is tabulated in Table 11.

Table 11: Deposition parameters for QPR samples

Procedure	Power (W)	Voltage (V)	Current (A)	Base Pressure (mbar)	Deposition Pressure (mbar)	Deposition temperature (°C)
SUBU	400	381	1.05	9×10^{-10}	3×10^{-3}	650
EP	400	385	1.04	7×10^{-10}	2×10^{-3}	650

3.3.1.1 SUBU prepared QPR

Figure 43: QPR images of: a) thermal heating; b) during deposition; c) after deposition

Figure 43 represents the visual inspection of the surface before, during and after deposition. It depicts that during the initial temperature ramp up regular white spot appeared corresponding to where the thermometer and heater holes at the back of the copper block are situated. These white spots persisted throughout the deposition and after the deposition.

3.3.1.2 EP prepared QPR

Figure 44: QPR images of: a) thermal heating; b) during deposition; c) after deposition

Figure 44 represents the visual inspection of the surface before, during and after deposition. It depicts that during the initial temperature ramp up regular white spots, which appeared on the SUBU prepared QPR did not materialised. However, during deposition there a network of small white spots appeared which were observed even after deposition and cooled down to room temperature. These white spots persisted throughout the deposition and after the deposition.

3.3.2 Deposition system at Siegen

In the initial ARIES report D15.1, results pertaining to the effects of different copper surface treatments on the superconducting performance of DCMS Nb thin films were presented. To further

understand the effects of the surface treatments, a series of Quadrupole Resonator (QPR) samples subjected to similar surface treatments were coated with similar niobium thin films. These samples were later tested at HZB in their QPR, under the influence of RF fields. Two samples have been coated at USI, samples B-2 and B-3. Both of these samples were initially treated at INFN Legnaro, prior to being coated at USI. Sample B-2 was initially treated with SUBU while sample B-3 was treated with an electropolishing process. Both of these processes were defined in D15.1. Following treatment at INFN, the sample was transported in a clean container under slight positive pressure in the presence of nitrogen.

The QPR samples were coated in the same industrial tool coating machine as the small NbN samples detailed previously. In order to reduce the likelihood of contamination, a flow cell was installed around the coating machine opening which ensured a continuous laminar flow across the coating machine entrance, displayed in Figure 45 (left). The samples were positioned on a substrate holder which is situated directly opposite the Nb target, where it is kept stationary during coating. This is shown in Figure 45 (right).

Figure 45: Image displaying (Left) flow cell installed around the coating machine opening and (Right) QPR sample installed inside coating machine.

The installation and coating of samples B-2 and B-3 followed a slightly different procedure. The procedure of sample B-2 will be described here. Following removal of sample B-2 from the transport

container, no further surface preparation was completed prior to installation (i.e. no gas blow). Following installation, but prior to deposition, the following procedures were followed:

- The chamber was baked out for 8 hours at 800 °C
- The chamber was cooled to room temperature to obtain base pressure of 5×10^{-7} hPa
- The chamber was reheated to the deposition temperature of 290 °C
- Substrate ion etching (Nb) process for 30 mins.
- Target cleaning process for 10 mins
- Deposition of thin film using DCMS with the following parameters:
 - Temperature: 290 °C
 - Pressure: 8×10^{-3} hPa
 - Cathode Power: 500 W
 - Process Gas: Argon
 - No substrate bias

This process resulted in a Nb film with a thickness of $\sim 2.1 \mu\text{m}$ being deposited which was verified with XRF measurements conducted at CERN. The surface is homogeneous with a total thickness variation of 7 % as shown in Figure 46. Initial visual inspection of the surface of sample B-2 showed evidence of some dust incorporation into the film during coating in the form of “spots” on the surface. This was examined further with an optical microscope, which confirmed the presence of contamination within the film as well as surface pitting from SUBU. The results are also presented in Figure 46.

As a result of this dust incorporation, the superconducting performance of this sample, as measured in the QPR, was not as good as expected. The transition temperature of the sample was $T_c = 9.5 \text{ K}$, indicating a stressed film, while the residual resistance at 415 MHz was $\sim 125 \text{ n}\Omega$. Further results and analysis is discussed in section 3.4. Following testing at HZB, the sample was sent to CERN for a second Nb coating using a HiPIMS coating process. The initial coating was stripped from the sample surface where after it was then treated with SUBU to mimic the initial SUBU process this sample received, thereby allowing comparison between the two coatings. The sample was then prepared with an HPR rinse, blow dried with N_2 and loaded into the coating system in a clean room along with four SUBU treated Cu witness samples. The coating system resembles a pillbox cavity, as shown in Figure 47, resulting in the QPR sample and witness samples being coated simultaneously on opposite sides of the cylindrical Nb target. Prior to deposition, the chamber was baked out at 200°C for 48 hours. The sample was then coated for 6 hours at a pressure of 2.4×10^{-3} hPa with a substrate temperature of roughly 200°C, resulting in a 7.3 μm thick film, as measured on the witness samples by XRF.

Figure 46: XRF film thickness results of sample B-2 (Top). Optical microscope images of sample B-2 surface (Bottom)

The sample is currently awaiting RF testing at CERN and will later be tested at HZB as well, allowing comparison between the two facilities as well. A series of investigations on the witness samples were also conducted at USI, with the results detailed below. The AFM scans, in size, were completed on one of the witness samples. The results show an RMS surface roughness of $S_q = 50.05 \pm 2.25 \mu\text{m}$. The roughness is seen to be a function of the area scanned as the film surface presents multiple different grain structures, some flat and others peaked in nature. The roughness is also likely enhanced due to the thickness of the film as well as the use of SUBU treatments for the Cu. A 3D image of the surface is shown in Figure 48. This information correlates well with SEM images displayed in Figure 48, which show a fairly flat surface comprised of a series of different grain formations, some of which are flat and some of which contain pronounced peaks.

Figure 47: QPR coating system used at CERN. Witness samples displayed on the left and QPR sample displayed on the right

Figure 48: (Left) AFM scan result of QPR witness sample and (Right) SEM image of the surface of the same witness sample.

The witness sample was also tested in the VSM at IEE. Results show a $T_c = 9.2$ K with an entry flux value of $B_{en} = 505$ Oe when measured in parallel field configuration. The in-plane texture of one of the witness samples was also investigated using XRD pole figures in stereographic projection. The sample was placed on the stage and analysed through an azimuthal angle of $0^\circ < \Phi < 360^\circ$ and a tilt

angle $0^\circ < \Phi < 85^\circ$. Pole figures for the {110} and {200} Nb planes were recorded and the results are presented in Figure 49. As shown, the film is strongly textured, displaying a (110) in-plane orientation.

Figure 49: XRD pole figures of a witness sample deposited with HiPIMS Nb

Following the results and lesson learned from the coating of sample B-2, the coating procedure for sample B-3 was adjusted slightly. Prior to installation into the coating machine, the sample surface was blown with ionised nitrogen to ensure the removal of all dust particles. Upon installation, a thorough inspection was performed to ensure this was achieved. Based on analysis of further small samples coated in between the two QPR samples, it was discovered that the ion etching process can result in the deposition of an interlayer between the substrate and the coating. In order to avoid this, the etching process was changed to an MF etching process which proved successful in pre-trials. During the coating of preparatory samples, the presence of voids at the interface between copper and the Nb film was also found. This is again unwanted as it could lead to localised heating and increased surface resistance according to the thermal boundary resistance model. In order to avoid this, a HiPIMS Nb interlayer was deliberately deposited with a thickness on the order of 200 nm, following successful pre-trials. The coating recipe itself was identical to that of sample B-2.

3.4 RF RESULTS

The transition from sheet samples to QPR samples made sample testing more complicated (albeit not as complicated as the transition to a real cavity would have been.).

Due to the peculiarities of the quadrupole resonators, it is necessary to perform a baseline RF test with an Nb coating on any of the QPR-samples prior to the test with the actual coating with SIS

multilayer or non-Nb material. This baseline test with a known and well-defined system ensures that any unexpected measured effect would not be falsely assigned to the new system. In case of a multilayer coating, the improvement imposed by the multilayer effect [1, 17] could be directly seen by comparison of the baseline measurement and the actual measurement of the multilayer. As will be detailed further below, this method unveiled problems with the initial samples, and the number of baseline RF-tests had to be increased. This is why only baseline tests of the Nb coated QPR samples can be reported at this point.

Table 12: QPR-sample processing schedule Highlighted in green are completed tests, red are failed tests, yellow colour stands for planned actions

Sample	Pre-treatment	SC coating	RF test	Next steps		
B-1	 3 µm Nb film	not performed	rewelding?			
B-2	RF test					
B-3	RF test					
B-4	RF test					
B-5	RF test					

However, these tests give invaluable information about possible show-stoppers for the film production: A series of systematic investigations was performed in order to evaluate the impact of the substrate treatment (SUBU or EP) on the SRF performance. Furthermore, the performance

difference of samples made in the different facilities (STFC and USI) was investigated. Table 12 shows a summary of the tests performed so far: Sample B-1 was milled to shape and SUBU treated at INFN, and subsequently coated with 3 μm of Niobium at STFC. Unfortunately, the sample exhibited a large leak along the Cu/Nb weld interface after processing, most likely because a significant layer of material had to be removed in the milling process in an attempt to remove a scratch on its surface. The QPR can deal with small vacuum leaks between sample interior and resonator chamber, but the encountered leak was so large that contamination of the “clean” resonator chamber with particles from the “dirty” thermometry chamber had to be feared. Besides this, the RF dissipation into the exposed gap was to be expected to dominate RF-losses on the exposed copper substrate and thus the measurement results. It was therefore decided not to perform an RF test on it. Instead, focus was shifted to the other 4 samples B-2, B-3, B-4, and B-5. B-2 and B-5 were SUBU treated at INFN and sent to USI and STFC respectively, B-3 and B-4 were EP treated at INFN and also sent to USI and STFC. Nb layer thickness was 3 μm on every sample apart from B-2 where it was 2 μm . RF tests with the HZB - QPR were performed on all samples.

3.4.1 Surface resistance as a function of applied field

The measurements of the four samples are displayed in Table 12: First, it needs to be stated that none of the QPR samples has reached the performance of the “typical” LHC cavities coatings (taken from [21, 22]), a clear indicator that further improvement of the coating procedures is necessary. Considering the asymptotic surface resistance values towards small fields and a temperature of 4.5 Kelvin, it becomes apparent that for both facilities, USI and STFC, the EP pre-treated substrate delivers better performance of the Nb film than the SUBU prepared substrates. SUBU treated substrates yield low-field surface resistance values of $\sim 150 \text{ n}\Omega$ in both facilities, while those values are improved to around $110 \text{ n}\Omega$ for the USI sample and even lower, $80 \text{ n}\Omega$, for the STFC sample. This is very similar to the reference bulk sample JN5³, but still significantly higher than values obtained for LHC cavities. The latter is very likely to be caused by systematic errors of the QPR measurement principle at low fields, which have been extensively investigated in previous EuCARD2 related experiments [23]. It is reasonably safe to assume that films from both facilities on the EP treated substrates perform sufficiently well for use in accelerators at low fields.

Samples from USI, generally show a higher residual resistance. As shown in Figure 50, the first sample (B-2) had a very high residual resistance and a quadratic field dependence of the surface resistance. On the other hand, the second sample (B-3 with EP and HIPIMS interlayer) shows a lower and more linear dependence up to 35 mT. The high residual resistance of the B-2 sample might be explained by large external inclusions on the surface, which were found by optical inspection, see Figure 43.

³ JN5 is a bulk Nb sample prepared at Jefferson Lab that has been used in previous experiments. It shows the best performance so far observed in the HZB QPR and is used as a reference for new samples

Figure 50: Measured surface resistance of samples B-2 and B-3 at ~416 MHz at 4.5 and 2.5 K.

Figure 51: Measured surface resistance of samples B-2 – B-5 at ~416 MHz and 4.5 K. LHC values and the reference bulk Nb sample JN5 are also plotted for comparison.

However, when going to higher B-fields, performance drawbacks of the produced Nb samples become apparent, see Figure 51. Three of four tested samples have shown “Q-switches” or

instantaneous increases of surface resistance when exceeding a certain field level. The origin of those Q-switches might be explained by overheating of small sections of the film without quenching the entire film. Although the true reason of those effects are not yet clear, it is suspected that the film quality might have an effect: Possibly this is caused by poor adhesion of the film. The measurements in a QPR are always dominated by the “worst” part of a sample.

Figure 52: Zoom-out of measured surface resistance of samples B-2 – B-5 at ~416 MHz and 4.5 K. LHC values and the reference bulk Nb sample JN5 are also plotted for comparison.

Comparison of samples produced at the STFC facility (B-4 and B-5) to the ones produced at University of Siegen (B-3 and B-2) generally shows a lower surface resistance for the STFC samples. However, the rapid resistance increase attributed to Q-switch occurs at lower fields. Hence, film adhesion appears to be better in the USI samples.

3.4.2 Surface resistance as a function of temperature

QPR-surface resistance measurements can be performed at different sample temperatures. In Figure 53 such measurements between 2 and 7 K and fixed magnetic fields are plotted. Here, the temperature-independent residual resistance has already been subtracted from the data and the BCS-

part of the surface resistance remains. Fitting the BCS resistance with its theoretical model yields several superconducting parameters that are listed in Table 13.

Figure 53: Measured BCS part of the surface resistance as a function of temperature at low field.

The transition temperature of the USI samples is generally higher, same as the penetration depth. From the penetration depth it can be derived that the RRR is lower for samples from USI (B-3 and B-4) compared to samples from STFC (B-4 and B-5 with RRR ~4-5).

The higher transition temperature of the samples from Siegen might be explained by a lattice mismatch between substrate and film, which imposes the Cu lattice structure on the grown film. This modified lattice structure has a direct effect on the energy gap and thus, the transition temperature of the superconductor. The lattice mismatch also puts the film under tension which is a reason for problems with the sticking of a film. This effect fits well with the observation that the transition temperature of the STFC films is closer to the bulk Nb transition temperature: Here, tension due to lattice mismatch might have been released at the cost of local detachment between substrate and superconductor film. The observed penetration depths which are higher in the Siegen samples, hinting at cleaner films, confirm this assumption.

Table 13: Materials parameters extracted from RF measurements with quadrupole resonator.

Sample	Pre-treatment	Nb coating facility	R_{res} [nΩ] 415 MHz	R_{res} [nΩ] 850 MHz	T_c [K]	λ_0 [nm] 415 MHz	λ_0 [nm] 850 MHz	λ_0 [nm] 1.29 GHz
B-2.4	SUBU	USI	95	-	9.48	120±5		
B-3.6	EP	USI	35..45	110	9.44	230±20	200±20	140±15
B-4.4	EP	STFC	~25	60	9.18	100±10	85±5	78±5
B-5.4	SUBU	STFC	~25	80	9.27	67±5		

3.4.3 Commissioning and benchmarking of the CERN QPR 2.0

At CERN, a second quadrupole resonator had been built. It was part of the ARIES scope, to benchmark both, HZB QPR and CERN QPR2 with an identical sample from the ones produced within ARIES.

Figure 54: Surface resistance of a test Nb sample measured in CERN QPR1 (left) and QPR 2.0 (right)

A pure Niobium sample from the batch ordered for ARIES at Research Instruments, was measured in both CERN QPRs. The measured surface resistance at 400 MHz, both at 2.5 and 4.5 K, is shown in Figure 54 for the two cases. As it can be appreciated, there is a significant discrepancy in the measured values, in particular at 4.5 K, where the surface resistance is higher. It must be noted that the quality of the sample was very poor, and high dissipation was evident even at low fields. This could be attributed to the large roughness of the surface ($R_a \sim 30\text{-}40 \mu\text{m}$). The QPR is not optimized for such high values of resistance, as there might be heat leaks affecting the accuracy of the calorimetric compensation, so that the measurement uncertainty is much increased.

A second QPR sample from the ARIES batch, B-2, was tested at CERN. The sample was received with an Nb layer on the Cu base at CERN, but it presented initially massive defects. For this reason, it was decided to strip the sample and coat it again. SUBU was applied during 20 minutes, followed by HPWR and finally an Nb layer was deposited with HiPIMS (-50 V bias), with a final thickness of 8 μm .

The characterization of this second sample, with CERN QPR1, was hampered by leaks from the helium bath to the thermometry chamber and to the QPR cavity, which obliged to warm up the cryostat for repairs. Once all the leaks were fixed, the measurements could restart on 13th March, but they were immediately stopped as the installations were closed due to the Covid-19 crisis. During the first (and only) day of measurements, some preliminary data were taken at 400 MHz and 2.5 K, but the sample needed further conditioning. It is planned to resume the measurement once the activity on site will restart.

4. Conclusions and future plans

The ARIES WP15 team made significant progress with the production of superconducting thin film coatings on copper samples. System 3 (NbTiN) and SIS (NbN:AlN:Nb, as well as Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb and NbTiN:AlN:Nb) has been deposited and characterised with surface characterisation instruments and DC magnetometry. Furthermore, the SIS structures (Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb₃Sn:AlN:Nb) and SS structures (Nb₃Sn:Nb, NbTiN:NbTiN, NbTi:Nb) have been investigated. It has demonstrated the capability of WP15 partners to develop different types of superconducting films and engineer their properties.

In order to demonstrate the films usability for SRF applications and to test them at RF conditions a number of films has been deposited on QPR-samples. To enable this, QPR samples for the RF characterisation of films were fabricated by HZB at Research Instruments, according to the information obtained with the sample procedures. The polishing procedure has been developed and optimised at INFN/LNL for EP and SUBU. A new facility for QPR-sample deposition has been built at STFC, the existing deposition facilities at Universität Siegen and CERN have been adapted for QPR-samples. RF tests have been performed at HZB and CERN. In total, 5 QPR samples have been produced, polished and tested by the WP15 partners. It was demonstrated that the WP15 partners are capable to scale up the production parameters for small samples to the significantly larger QPR samples and to produce state-of-the art Nb baseline coatings. The resulting low-power RF surface resistances are in the same order of magnitude as LHC cavities. However, these first samples produced by WP15 partners suffer from Q-jump at high powers. The causes of these Q-jumps will be investigated in the following year.

For the remainder of the ARIES project, further sample treatment and polishing activities are planned:

- The electropolished samples have been chosen for following up on the original scope to test advanced superconductor coatings:
 - Sample B-3 will be shipped back from HZB to USI and coated with an SIS multilayer, consisting of a new 3 μ m Nb layer, a 30 nm AlN insulator layer, and finally a 100 nm NbN layer
 - Sample B-4 will be shipped to INFN for another electropolishing step, and from there sent to STFC for a SIS multilayer coating which is yet to be decided.
- It is foreseen, to perform a laser post-treatment step with the SUBU sample B-5 at Riga university and investigate if film adhesion can be improved by remelting the film with a laser
- Sample B-2 will be tested in the CERN QPR, and then sent back to HZB for a direct comparison of RF results on the same sample

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AFM	Atomic Force Microscope
CEA	Saclay Nuclear Research Centre - Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique
CERN	European Council for Nuclear Research
EDS	Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectrometry
EP	Electropolishing
HIPIMS	High power impulse magnetron sputtering

HZB	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin
IEE	Institute of Electrical Engineering Slovak Academy of Sciences, Bratislava
INFN-LNL	Italian Institute of Nuclear Physics - Legnaro National Laboratories
OFE	Oxygen Free Electronic copper
OFHC	Oxygen-Free High thermal Conductivity copper
PPMS	Physical Property Measurement System
QPR	Quadrupole Resonator
QWR	Quarter Wave Resonator
RF	Radio Frequency
RTU	Riga Technical University
SC	Superconductivity
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope
SRF	Superconducting Radio Frequency
STFC	Science and Technology Facilities Council - Daresbury Laboratory
SUBU	Chemical Polishing of Cu with a solution of Sulphamic Acid and Butanol
T_c	Critical temperature of superconducting transition (thermodynamic)
TF	Thin films
USI	University of Siegen
XRD	X-Ray Diffraction